

DEVELOPMENT OF FLEXIBLE WATERPROOFING MORTAR FROM GEOPOLYMER

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Since the production and application of cement are not environmentally sustainable, geopolymers can be a green alternative utilized in building chemicals. In this study, Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) in the formula of a two-component mortar was tried to decrease by replacing geopolymer. Firstly, different formulas of geopolymers were cured at ambient conditions by using different ratios of fly ash/blast furnace slag, a fixed concentration of NaOH solution, a fixed weight ratio of Na₂SiO₃/NaOH, and different ratios of solid/liquid. The geopolymerization yields were monitored by XRD and FTIR. According to the yields, three geopolymers were chosen. After the application, the performance tests such as crack bridging (EN1062-7 and EN 14891), determination of liquid water permeability (EN 1062-3), and measurement of bond strength by pull-off tests (EN 1542) were performed. According to the results compared to the reference mortar, the sample having geopolymer J3 as 75% of OPC has the optimum properties.